

How Financial Incentives Impact Clinical Trial Enrollment

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ABSTRACT

Clinical trials are critically important for medical advancement, as they provide scientifically valid data on new medications and drugs being developed. Many researchers, however, struggle with outreach to socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, leading to underrepresentation and exclusion of those demographics in clinical trials. This lack of representation leads to health disparities because marginalized groups may not receive treatments optimized for their needs, which results in therapies that are less effective or have unexpected side effects. Failing to include diverse groups can result in missed opportunities to discover insights about how different populations respond to therapies.

This paper provides an analysis of English-language clinical trials that include financial incentives in their procedures. Trial designs varied across studies; some were conducted online rather than in person, and some included hospitalized participants while others did not. Payment strategies were either constant or varied. These different trial designs all had unique impacts on the results of the experiment. Incentives also raised some ethical concerns in terms of a lack of transparency in regulations and safety hazards. However, there is not enough detailed research on the impacts of financial incentives; more experiments on the specific effects (undue inducement) and best way of providing incentives should be conducted. It is important to conduct more research on this to promote diversity and accessibility of clinical trials in order to ensure more equitable access to healthcare.

Keywords: *clinical trials, enrollment, socioeconomics, incentives*

1. INTRODUCTION

Clinical trials have been at the forefront of medical experimentation and innovation for decades. Yet, as modern medicine and treatments continue to develop, there is an ever increasing

need for sufficiently large and representative population samples that lead to valid and generalizable conclusions (Fahey et al., 2023). This is a particularly pressing issue, as clinical trials determine the safety and efficacy of new medical procedures. If people with lower incomes are underrepresented in clinical trials, skewed datasets may prevent those who were excluded from obtaining the same medical benefits.

As such, it is imperative that we begin to address the lack of diversity in clinical trials to ensure that underrepresented populations benefit from the solutions that derive from medical research. Limited recruitment of diverse populations may lead to inaccurate results due to a lack of ability to generalize to the broader population. In fact, a 2013 study by the Fred Hutchinson Cancer Research Center revealed that patients with an income of less than \$50,000 were 27% less likely to participate in clinical trials (Schoch, 2023). This lack of representation leads to delays, increased expenditures, decreased data accuracy, and lower trial quality (Idnay et al., 2023). However, financial incentives may increase participation among underprivileged populations through compensation of their time and efforts. This literature review aims to examine the effectiveness of monetary incentives on clinical trial enrollment.

2. METHODOLOGY

PubMed, a free database of biomedical literature, was used to begin research. Because of its large collection of free studies and peer-reviewed content, PubMed is a reliable and accessible resource for recent literature on this subject.

Three searches were conducted to find research that had been conducted between 2014 and 2024. The first search included a search for “‘incentive’ AND ‘clinical trials’ AND ‘enrollment’”. For the second search, “‘compensation’ AND ‘clinical trials’ AND ‘enrollment’” used as keywords. The last search included the terms “‘monetary’ AND ‘clinical trials’ AND ‘enrollment’”. The three searches resulted in a total of 78 papers. Papers were then excluded because of irrelevant titles and abstracts, the type of data collected, or the way in which results were analyzed. Of the 78 papers identified, seven (8.97%) were chosen for this review because they focused on financial incentives in trial enrollment and included relevant data on how financial incentives impact enrollment (Figure 1). These papers explored monetary incentives as a potential solution to improve clinical trial enrollment, and the authors conducted experiments

examining the effect of different payment distribution methods on participation. Additionally, for all the papers included in this study, the similar articles identified in PubMed were reviewed, but no additional papers were identified meeting the inclusion criteria. These search terms were also used to run searches in the Cochrane Library. No additional articles that fit the criteria were found, as the goal of this paper was to examine the impacts of utilizing compensation in clinical trials rather than observing clinical trials that used compensation.

Figure 1. Study inclusion criteria

3. RESULTS

The range of financial incentives offered from the seven studies were from \$0 to \$500. Of these seven trials, two (28.57%) offered maximum incentives below \$10 (Krutsinger et al., 2019;

Fahey et al., 2023), two (28.57%) offered maximum incentives between \$10 and \$100 (Campbell et al., 2024; Meier et al. 2024), one (14.29%) offered maximum incentives above \$100 (Halpern et al., 2021), and two (28.57%) did not specify the maximum incentive amount offered (Bierer et al., 2021; Idnay et al., 2023).

Trial methods, including incentive payment timelines, varied across all seven studies. Of the five studies that included the incentive amounts, two provided unconditional compensation while three provided randomized compensation. Unconditional compensation refers to participants receiving a set amount of money, while randomized compensation refers to participants receiving an arbitrarily selected amount of money within a certain range (Table 1). In addition, three of these trials were conducted digitally, through either a web or app-based platform, which may limit their generalizability since these digital platforms simply allow enrollees to register and complete tasks online without much scrutiny about who the respondents are.

Table 1. Trial design summary

The papers by Idnay et al. and Bierer et al. were not included as they did not have a trial-based experimental design.

Study	Amount Offered	Hypothesis Tested
Campbell et al. (2024)	Base of \$25; additional \$5 for each peer enrolled	Whether incentivized peer enrollment impacts trial participation
Fahey et al. (2023)	Unconditional \$5	Whether an unconditional reward impacted subsequent enrollment
Halpern et al. (2021)	\$0, \$200, or \$500 for the smoking cessation trial; \$0, \$100, or \$300 for the ambulation trial	Whether incentives improve enrollment or serve undue inducements
Krutsinger et al. (2019)	Unconditional \$1	Whether disbursement strategies impacted enrollment

Meier et al. (2024)	Randomly generated amount between \$0 and \$50	Whether the amount of money impacted enrollment
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3.1 Trial Design

One study conducted by Halpern et al. (2021) considered two separate trials on smoking cessation and ambulation (walking or moving around). The smoking cessation trial offered incentives of either \$0, \$200, or \$500 while the ambulation trial offered incentives of either \$0, \$100, or \$300. These amounts were chosen based on how much effort the participants would have to exert. In the smoking trial, incentives increased the rate of participants enrolling proportionally to the amount offered. When compared to a baseline anticipated enrollment rate of 50%, enrollment in the smoking cessation trial increased in 47 of 216 (21.8%) when a \$0 incentive was offered, 78 of 217 (35.9%) when a \$200 incentive was offered, and 104 of 221 (47.1%) when a \$500 incentive was offered. However, incentives did not significantly increase participation in the ambulation trial: increased in 98 of 216 (45.4%) when a \$0 incentive was offered, 102 of 212 (48.1%) when a \$100 incentive was offered, and 92 of 214 (43.0%) when a \$300 incentive was offered. This is likely due to the patient population; those participating in the ambulation trial were already hospitalized while those participating in the smoking cessation trial were not. The participants for the ambulation trial also did not have any transportation or scheduling barriers that would disrupt their jobs or errands. Thus, there was little need for ambulation trial enrollees to find a way to offset the costs of participating in a trial. On the other hand, those registering for the smoking cessation trial may have been more motivated by an incentive to participate due to the need to take time off from their daily work schedules. The variability of these results due to the trial design is an important consideration for future studies in making their experiments more comparable. For example, researchers should use a standardized measurement scale that accounts for the time taken out of participants' daily routines and the amount compensated.

In another three studies, trials were conducted digitally either through an app or the web. In the trial conducted by Fahey et al. (2023), an unconditional monetary incentive of \$5 was offered to potential registrants. As a result, enrollment increased by 9%, a statistically significant

increase. However, because the enrollment approach was online, some key demographics, like lower socioeconomic status or older age, were inadvertently excluded.

This result is drastically different from the trial coordinated by Meier et al (2024), where participants were given a randomly generated compensation amount between \$0 and \$50. In this case, willingness to enroll was not impacted by compensation, as the data showed a very slight and nonsignificant correlation between the two. This is likely due to the fact that the research was conducted through a mobile app; 54% of participants noted that having to download the app was the reason that they decided to not continue with the study even though they were aware of how much compensation they would receive. Requiring participants to download an app may have increased barriers for certain populations who might not have had access to the Internet or a mobile device. From these two studies, online enrollment has mixed results; generally, enrollment increases when incentives are offered, but often at the expense of including certain populations.

In another trial performed by Krutsinger et al. (2019), the following five financial payment strategies were used: (1) constant (in which participants received the same amount of money each week); (2) increasing (in which participants received growing amounts of money each week); (3) U-shaped (in which participants received more money at the beginning and the end of the trial); (4) surprise (in which participants received random amounts of money from week to week); or (5) self-select (in which participants chose which payment strategy they wanted). While this study examined the effects of financial incentives on both enrollment and retention, only the enrollment results are discussed here since they are the focus of this review paper. By the end of the trial, each participant received the same total amount of money.

None of the four experimental financial incentive strategies explored in Krutsinger et al. (2019) increased enrollment compared to the constant financial incentive strategy (Table 2). Due to the fact that this trial was conducted on a web-based platform, incentive strategies did not impact participants much because the convenience of hosting a clinical study on the web ensured that there were few transportation or scheduling barriers. As a result, the already high enrollment rates may have minimized the impact of offering an incentive. However, in a real world setting, the impact of each financial distribution strategy may change, as participants would have to consider other factors impacting their ability to enroll.

Table 2. Participant burdens and observed effects of incentives

The papers by Idnay et al., Campbell et al., and Bierer et al. were not included because they did not include a specific measurable outcome evaluating the impact of incentives on patient enrollment.

Study	Participant Burden	Observed Effects
Halpern et al. (2021)	Participants in the ambulation trial were hospitalized while those in the smoking trial were not.	The ambulation trial saw no significant increase in enrollment while the smoking cessation trial saw proportional increase in enrollment to the amount offered.
Fahey et al. (2023)	Enrollment was offered online.	Although there was a 9% increase in enrollment, participants of older age and lower socioeconomic status were inadvertently excluded.
Meier et al. (2024)	Participants had to download an app to participate and receive monetary compensation.	There was no significant increase in enrollment largely due to the requisite of downloading an app.
Krutsinger et al. (2019)	Five different disbursement strategies were used to pay participants.	None of the different payment strategies impacted enrollment likely due to the study being conducted online, removing the inconvenience of travel and taking time off work.

3.2 Payment Strategies

Unlike Krutsinger et al. (2019), a trial conducted by Campbell et al. (2024) found that a payment strategy based on peer referral can result in a large increase in study enrollment. In their study, enrollees were offered a \$5 incentive, which resulted in an initial jump in an average of 2.007 recruitments and then an average of 0.0174 recruitments in each subsequent week. This incentivized peer referral (IPR) program resulted in a population study in which 21.9% of the participants were referred to the study by another participant (Table 3). IPR may be a good strategy to use because of its convenience. IPR also minimizes advertisement barriers like digital promotions, and a lack of familiarity by participants. By offering an incentive for enrollees to refer others, trial enrollment not only increased, but participation also grew within specific demographic groups since referred respondents were often similar to the people who referred them. This research demonstrates that IPR is an effective way to engage participants in research programs.

Table 3. Variable incentive trial summary

The papers by Fahey et al., Ichnay et al., Meier et al., Halpern et al., and Bierer et al., were not included because they did not utilize a trial design of variable incentives and instead evaluated the impact of one fixed incentive amount.

Study	Incentive Structure	Observed Effects
Krutsinger et. al (2019)	Unconditional \$1 Five different disbursement strategies were used to pay participants.	None of the different payment strategies impacted enrollment likely due to the study being conducted online, removing the inconvenience of travel and taking time off work.
Campbell et. al (2023)	Base of \$25; additional \$5 for each peer enrolled.	There was a jump in people referred with subsequent enrollments each week, resulting in a study population

		where nearly 22% of those participating were referred.
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3.3 Ethical Considerations

Although participant compensation is positively associated with recruitment success, there are several drawbacks to offering monetary incentives for enrollment (Idnay et al., 2023). Idnay et al. (2023) experimented using “multi-source retrospective data analysis [with] machine learning methods,” and found that compensation has a large and significant impact in terms of enrollment. However, offering incentives to enroll also led to several drawbacks, including less time spent reading about the risks of clinical trials and potential exploitation of marginalized populations. This creates a need to ensure there are pertinent safeguards in place to lessen the probability of participants ignoring critical details and research unintentionally excluding certain groups of people.

Another trial conducted by Bierer et al. (2021) highlights the potential concerns of utilizing incentives to increase study enrollment. Individuals from low-income backgrounds are often underrepresented and understudied in clinical trials due to lack of resources or financial burdens imposed by said trials. As such, offering an incentive for enrollment may be an “undue inducement” for populations that truly need the financial resources (Table 4). Because incentives often go beyond what is considered appropriate reimbursement (for expenses) or compensation (for time and research-related burdens), Bierer et al. (2021) argues that some participants may conceal important information in order to have access to and participate in the study to receive payments. This results in an increased need to ensure transparency of medical records to mitigate potential risks of patient health and clinical trial integrity.

Table 4. Potential negative impacts of a financial incentive

Only two trials are included in this table because only two studies reported on negative outcomes.

Study	Impact on Enrollment	Negative Outcomes
Idnay et. al	Compensation had a very large impact in enrollment with a p-value less than 0.05.	Less time was spent reading about the risks of clinical trials, leading to potential safety hazards.
Bierer et. al	Individuals from low socioeconomic status may be more willing to participate in clinical trials without fully understanding the risks.	Undue inducement may occur as well as enrollees concealing important information just to get the compensation.

4. DISCUSSION

Financial incentives seem to have the most effect on clinical trials that are conducted in person as opposed to online. In trials that required participants to be on-site, financial incentives resulted in a statistically significant increase in enrollment, while trials held online saw little to no increase in enrollment when offering incentives. Payment distribution strategies had nearly no effect on enrollment since participants were aware of the monetary amount beforehand. Although financial incentives increased enrollment rates, they also resulted in potential ethical hazards in which participants neglected to consider risks associated with registering.

In light of the findings from this review, researchers should consider the ethical implications of offering certain amounts of financial incentives. In the future, more studies should aim to gain a more holistic understanding of how financial incentives affect clinical research results. This may include examining whether higher financial incentives are linked to an increased risk of undue inducement, or experiments that use more consistent methods of distributing incentives. Future studies should offer the same type of incentive for a more uniform approach instead of offering participants a mix of debit cards, cash, or checks. Incentives are a

noteworthy way of improving enrollment, but they must be offered in a way that avoids undue inducement and exploitation.

5. CONCLUSION

Research shows that financial incentives can significantly increase clinical trial enrollment. Providing compensation attracts more participants by alleviating concerns about transportation costs, time off work, and other financial burdens. The way the studies are conducted also impact results. The studies identified for inclusion in this paper provided a large range of compensation, anywhere from \$0 to \$500, which had varying effects on how much of an increase there was in enrollment. Additionally, different ways of distributing money, such as constant compensation or incentivized peer referral, had varying effects on the number and demographic of people enrolling. As such, more research is needed to understand the most optimal incentive structure for encouraging enrollment in a safe and effective way.

6. LIMITATIONS

This literature review only examines randomized clinical trials that have been conducted within the last ten years. Any studies conducted earlier may have had varying results or used different incentive strategies. Similarly, because this review only focuses on randomized clinical trials, there is an abundance of other research that was not included in the three searches on PubMed.

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